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Project Ô Website
www.eu-project-o.eu

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Implementing practical tools for

WATER SUSTAINABILITY

Water scarcity is a human-made problem

Water supply often struggles to cope with demand. As a result, the UN forecasts the world could face a 40% deficit in water supply by 2030.

Project Ô shows how **local, targeted** water treatment and filtration technologies can help **improve global water management**, allowing current and future generations **to benefit from this shared resource**.

Mission

Project Ô's mission is to show how local water reuse can benefit water management as part of a circular economy leading to a more reliable supply and increasing resilience to economic and environmental changes.

Project Ô enables water management and treatment technologies for large and small water treatment facilities

The combination of innovative treatment technologies with two digital platforms will improve water management for communities in Europe and beyond

Solutions

Four modules combining different water treatment and filtration technologies and two digital platforms have been developed to meet distinct water management challenges, enabling a circular water economy.

ADV.ERT MODULE

Accessing untapped water sources that are inaccessible for existing water treatment plants, through desalination and the removal of contaminants.

PHOTO.CAT MODULE

Removing complex pollutants from used textile production water to save resources and energy, and protect the local environment.

MOBILE3TECH MODULE

Removing toxic pollutants from used industrial water to protect water treatment plants, increase water reuse and meet new regulations.

SALTECH MODULE

Ensuring mariculture meets new regulations, improving resource management and creating commercial opportunities.

DECISION ANALYTIC PLATFORM

Supporting water regulators to make robust and efficient management decisions based on current and future conditions.

CIRCULAR ECONOMY PLATFORM

Business-facing solution to support local water reuse between users involved in water treatment and management activities.

Project Ô solutions

- ✓ **Customisable**
Water regulators and facility managers can choose the technologies to match their specific needs.
- ✓ **Cost-effective**
By treating individual streams of used water, reusing water and only applying needed treatments.
- ✓ **Scalable**
SMEs can manage their own water footprint, while larger companies can complement their existing processes.
- ✓ **Sustainable**
Taking a holistic approach to ensure social, economic, cultural and environmental sustainability.